

THE IMPACT OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING UNIT IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS AROUND ENUGU METROPOLIS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878853>

Published Date: 29-April-2023

Abstract: Education developed from human struggle for survival and enlightenment. It is an act of acquiring skill passed on from generation to generation for the development and comfort of mankind. Generally education has been developing at all levels hence the need to fortify and sustain it with the help of guidance and counseling. Guidance and counseling programme in secondary schools includes bringing to the students an increased understanding of the educational, vocational and social information needed to make wise choices in life. It is a form of education which the students receive from their school counselors in order to eliminate overwhelming ignorance on their career choices/prospects and personality maladjustment among school children. Therefore it is recommended that guidance and counseling be included in the school time table for it to be effective and impact on the life of our youths.

Keywords: Counselor, Vocation, Psychotherapeutic, Adolescent, Globalization, Career, Catharsis, Probing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is said to be an accumulated experience that has a determined effect on human character and mind. As a process through which societal values, norms, principles, ethics and skills can be adequately conveyed, individuals need education in order to acquire this accumulated knowledge. The educational system in Nigeria is not far from the technical aspects of education, in that it is all involving as a process of transmitting the societal norms and values towards the development of the Nation. An overview of the colonial educational system provided, revealed gross inadequacy, unsatisfactory to the educational ingenuity, yearning and aspirations of the people. Thus many scholars opined that this formal education was parochial, elitist, regurgitate and irresponsive to the need and aspirations of the Nigerian society. National Policy on Education (2004).

In Nigeria, the organized guidance and counseling started in 1959 at St. Theresa's college Oke Ada in Ibadan, Oyo State by some Reverend Sisters out of concern for the products of their school. These Reverend Sisters were aware of the importance of guidance and counseling services in preparing many young people to define and redefine their goals and aspirations in life pursuits for greater productivity. Afterwards, the vocational guidance services spread to other public secondary schools in the Country. Officials from the Ministry of Education became interested in these organized services that this group of "career advisers" were invited to provide career talks and workshops for teachers and career masters. National Policy on Education (2004).

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Research Design:

This research was descriptive in form and adopted the ex-*post facto* design. It enabled inferences to be drawn about the relationships that exist among variables without direct interaction from concomitant variables. Put in the other way, my

interest was in determining the influence guidance and counseling services have on students in secondary schools when exposed to counseling services and when they are not, without any manipulation. Results were generalized on the sample size investigated portraying the differences in the entire population.

Population of the study:

A sample of ten percent (10%) of the target population is representative (Gysbery and Henderson, 2005). In line with this twelve out of the schools with practicing counselors participated in the study.

Sample and sampling technique:

Fourteen schools were sampled, one federal government college, one university secondary school and twelve public secondary schools. In all twenty counselors responded to the questionnaire on guidance services.

Instrument for data collection:

The instrument used for data collection called guidance services questionnaire (GSQ) consisted of two sections "A" and "B". The "A" part took care of the Bio-data while the "B" segmented the items into three i.e. educational, vocational and personal/social issues.

Method of data analysis:

The completed questionnaire was collected and their responses were collated, ratio and percentages were used in presenting the results.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study were presented in Tables 1 and 2 below.

Table 1: Show the most regularly performed guidance services in the schools studied.

SERVICE	Nos. of schools rendering Such service.	Percentage of school rendering the service.
Academic counseling	5	42%
Vocational counseling	2	18%
Personal/social counseling	1	8%
Orientation	1	8%
Placement	1	8%
Appraisal testing	1	8%
Excursion	1	8%

Table 1. Show the major guidance services rendered by the schools. Academic counseling service is the one most regularly performed by counselors. Students with difficulties in reading, comprehension, study habit and examination preparation skills, slow learners and chronically failing students can be assisted through academic counseling. These are crucial aspects in the children's learning process that should be addressed to achieve the desired quality.

Table 2: Show the number of students utilizing guidance and counseling services per week.

School	Academic counseling	Vocational counseling	Personal/Social counseling
School A	90	50	24
School B	30	25	47
School 1	40	27	27
School 2	50	40	7
School 3	40	40	7
School 4	10	5	4
School 5	25	25	7
School 6	150	160	37

School 7	100	150	47
School 8	30	20	7
School 9	40	20	7
School 10	100	20	47
School 11	100	10	47
School 12	40	2	7

In general, most of the schools studied show that counselors attend more to students with the need for academic counseling. Subsequently, vocational and personal/social counseling comes next in the hierarchy of needs. However, most counselors remarked that they were not able to carry out these functions satisfactorily because they were saddled with classroom teaching and general administrative duties assigned to them by their school principals.

4. CONCLUSION

As a result of the findings from this research, it then stands to reason that if students are to cope with the challenges of academic activities, guidance and counseling as an educational service should be properly implemented to the later in schools, as proposed by the Federal Government (National Policy on Education, 2004).

Efforts of the Government should be directed towards the training of more teachers and specifically counselors, if our desire for quality in our educational system will be achieved. It is clear from the results of this study that shortage of trained teachers in schools effects the services of counselors who are often used to fill the gap to the neglect of their counseling duties. The impact of guidance and counseling in terms of awareness is felt in most of our schools and its recognition, acceptance and utilization as a vital service in the school system is still far from being a reality.

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